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Blockchain-Enabled RF Radiation Exposure Level Measurement in Wireless Mobile Networks

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Abstract—The expansion of telecommunication providers and their efforts to expand network coverage in Sri Lanka has led to an alarming increase in Radio Frequency (RF) radiation exposure. This heightened exposure has raised concerns about its potential adverse effects on human health. Despite the country’s growing number of cancer cases, no apparent cause has been identified. This research aims to identify areas exposed to harmful RF radiation levels through the innovative application of blockchain technology. The methodology involves measuring RF radiation in densely populated locations and implementing a blockchain-based spectral power misuse detection system via mobile networks. This system notifies users of harmful RF radiation exposure through an Android app. In this system, the collected data is first clustered and then aggregated after removing potential “outlier” data points, before adding the data to the blockchain. These two steps are important to increase the performance of the blockchain network, which is evaluated based on performance metrics, including success rate, latency, throughput, and memory usage of the blockchain. The data is analyzed in the blockchain network to detect if there are harmful signal levels in the country and to alert the users if there are any.

Index Terms—RF Radiation Detection, Blockchain, Grid-Based Clustering, RANSAC Method, Data Aggregation

I. INTRODUCTION

In the past few years, the rate of human deaths due to cancers has increased exponentially in Sri Lanka [1]. It is believed that exposure to higher Radio Frequency (RF) levels in mobile towers is harmful to humans. In particular, RF radiation has been classified as a “possible human carcinogen” by the World Health Organization (WHO) [2] and the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) [3]. In particular, MR Miah et al. in [4] have examined the potential impact of processed RF on the pancreas and its potential to cause diabetes among exposed people. With the increase in demand for telecommunication services, service providers are attempting to improve the coverage of their networks by adding more base stations, which are often located in urban areas. Therefore, it is essential to measure the level of RF exposure for people close to these stations, to ensure it is safe for human exposure. The Telecommunications Regulatory Commission of Sri Lanka (TRCSL) follows the standards defined by the International Commission on Non-Ionized Radiation Protection (ICNIRP) [5] and defines regulations for

local service providers to maintain proper RF levels in mobile towers.

Because of the issues mentioned above, there is a growing need for innovative solutions within the telecommunication sector. With the advent of Web3 [6] and related decentralized applications, blockchain technology emerges as a viable solution for modern applications, including those in the telecommunication sector, owing to its security and decentralized features. is a promising technology that can be used in such telecommunication applications. Rajat Kochhar et al. in the paper [7], have proposed several blockchain-based use cases for telecommunication networks, including identity management, fraud prevention IoT security, and initial coin offerings. S.Y. Wang et al. in [8] have discussed integrating blockchain technology into wireless sensor networks (WSNs) for data collection and analysis, which demonstrates improved execution efficiency compared to traditional methods. The authors emphasize the security and reliability of blockchain technology. Furthermore, state-of-the-art approaches to spectrum management using blockchain technology have been proposed in the literature [9], [10].

This research aims to study the levels of RF radiation in the country. Also, the study aims to use blockchain technology to detect misuse of RF spectrum power and to develop a mobile application to alert users about areas with harmful radiation levels. The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section II presents the system architecture. Section III shows the numerical results and the discussion, and Section IV concludes the paper.

II. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The overall architecture of the proposed blockchain-enabled RF radiation exposure level measurement system is shown in Fig. 1.

The operation of the proposed overall system is as follows.

- 1) **Data sent from mobile devices:** The location data and the signal levels in that area are measured from the mobile devices and sent periodically to the mobile edge device located at the base station, from where they are clustered and aggregated.

Fig. 1: Proposed Blockchain-Enabled RF Radiation Exposure Level Measurement Architecture.

- 2) **Data added to the blockchain:** After clustering and aggregation, the data is added to the Hyperledger Fabric network for further analysis.
- 3) **Firestore Cloud Messaging (FCM) tokens are added to the Blockchain:** The unique token of each mobile device is also updated periodically on the blockchain.
- 4) **High RF radiation level is detected:** When a high RF radiation level is detected, a request is sent to Firestore Cloud Messaging API along with the location to send a notification to the users.
- 5) **Relevant user tokens are queried:** When the request for a notification is received, the FCM tokens of users related to the given location are queried from the blockchain network.
- 6) **Notifications sent:** After receiving the user tokens, the notifications are sent to the mobile devices with these tokens, alerting them that they are potentially being exposed to high RF radiation levels.

This Fig.1 only gives an overview of the system's operation, and an in-depth explanation of each of these components is given in the following subsections.

A. Developing a Mobile Application

The mobile application incorporates several key features to implement the intended workflow in Fig. 1. The measured data and FCM tokens and their locations have been transmitted and recorded on the blockchain. Also, the users in areas with high RF radiation levels must be alerted through a notification. Those areas must be displayed in the dynamic map in the mobile application, shown in Fig. 2. Here, Fig.2a shows how the users will be notified using push notifications and Fig 2b illustrates how the harmful locations are indicated in the dynamic map of the mobile application.

B. Developing an Aggregation Mechanism

Data Aggregation is a technique used to combine multiple data points into a single value. The data collected from the

Fig. 2: Notifying Harmful Locations to the Users.

mobile application may have repetitions and faulty readings. Testing each RF level consumes resources, and faulty data can mislead users. An appropriate aggregation method helps overcome these challenges, filtering out outliers and enhancing system reliability.

The most common outlier detection methods used for any type of data distribution are Tukey's method and the Random Sampling Consensus (RANSAC) method. When considering these two methods, RANSAC is robust, adaptable, and efficient for handling outliers and large datasets in RF signal research. In contrast, Tukey's method, relying on medians, may struggle with complex patterns and is less user-friendly, with high computational demands for large datasets.

Considering the above comparison of the RANSAC method and Turkey's method, the RANSAC method is chosen and customized according to the research requirements to identify the inliers and remove outliers. Configuring the RANSAC model involves selecting four key parameters. The number of points required to fit a line (n) is set to 2 to maximize the combinations of data points for iteration. The maximum number of iterations (k) is 1000, as increasing iterations enhances system accuracy. Inlier tolerance (t) is set at 15dB for simplicity. The RANSAC model order is fixed at 1 for computational simplicity, resulting in a straight-line fit. These parameter choices cater to varied research requirements, balancing computational efficiency and flexibility for customization.

Fig. 3 illustrates the outlier detection of the RANSAC method according to the parameter values we mentioned above. The data points with a value greater than the inlier tolerance (t) are detected as outliers, and the data points with a value lesser or equal to the inlier tolerance(t) are detected as inliers.

C. Clustering Methods

Clustering is a process of grouping the received data points. In this research, a proper clustering mechanism is needed to group the RF data so that the system can easily detect the areas where harmful RF signals are transmitted and alert the users.

Fig. 3: Outlier Detection in Galle Fort Using RANSAC Method.

Fig. 4: Illustration of Grid Based Clustering Method for Cluster Size of $111 \times 111 m^2$.

Grid-based clustering method was selected for our system as it can be easily implemented on large data sets and simplifies the complexity of clustering algorithms by working with a predefined grid structure.

According to the research requirement, we customized the Grid-Based clustering method. Here, a grid with small cells wastes resources and increases the system’s complexity. Also, having very large grid cells affects the accuracy of the system and makes it difficult to detect harmful signals as the data set is very large. In this study, we developed an algorithm where the latitude and longitude values of a data point are rounded off to a certain decimal point, which will group nearby data into a square-shaped cluster. Considering the aread of the resulting clusters, we have rounded off the latitude and longitude values up to three decimal points which provides $111 \times 111 m^2$ grid cells. Fig. 4 shows a map of Galle, Sri Lanka, illustrating these clusters defined by the grid system we have used in this study.

D. Implementation of Blockchain

In this work, we have used Hyperledger Fabric, a robust and permissioned blockchain network, for storing and analyzing

users’ location and signal-level data. In fact, it ensures that only authorized entities can participate in the network and access the stored data. Unlike public blockchains, Hyperledger Fabric allows for fine-grained control over access rights, making it suitable for applications where privacy is important.

To ensure the integrity and consistency of the distributed ledger, we have implemented the RAFT consensus algorithm within our Hyperledger Fabric network. RAFT is a robust consensus protocol that guarantees fault tolerance and leader election, ensuring that all nodes in the network agree on the order and validity of transactions. This consensus mechanism enhances the reliability of our radiation monitoring and notification solution.

In our Hyperledger Fabric implementation, we have prioritized security through the utilization of default Membership Service Providers (MSPs) and Certificate Authorities (CAs). The default CA hierarchy, comprising Root CA and Intermediate CAs, issues certificates to authenticate participants, while MSPs manage identities and access rights. This setup ensures the integrity of our blockchain network. Organizations, peers, and orderers adhere to MSPs, enforcing access controls based on roles defined in Node Organization Units. By relying on these default security mechanisms, our implementation establishes a secure environment for data transmission, user authentication, and transaction integrity within the Hyperledger Fabric network.

Within our Hyperledger Fabric network, we have implemented two key smart contracts, known as chaincodes:

- “Level” chaincode: This chaincode records and processes clustered and aggregated signal strength information. Additionally, it facilitates the display of locations with high signal levels on the dynamic map of the mobile application.
- “Token” chaincode: Complementing the “Level” chaincode, the “Token” chaincode records the periodic locations of mobile application users. When the “Level” chaincode detects high radiation levels in a specific area, the location data from the “Token” chaincode is used to notify users.

III. NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

As discussed in Section II, collected data are clustered and aggregated before being sent to the blockchain network. By doing this, the number of data points processed in the blockchain is reduced through clustering, and their accuracy is increased by removing outliers and aggregating. Therefore, the performance analysis is done on the Hyperledger Fabric network by considering two cases: without clustering and aggregation mechanisms and with those mechanisms.

We used Hyperledger Caliper as the benchmarking tool for the performance analysis, assuming a user base of 1250 for the mobile application. 10000 requests were sent to the system to measure the blockchain network’s success rate, latency, and throughput. Also, in both cases, the growth of the blockchain was monitored for 2 minutes to measure the memory usage of the nodes.

Fig. 5: Performance Parameters of the Fabric Network.

A. Case 1: Without Clustering and Aggregation Mechanisms

When data is not clustered and aggregated before being sent to the blockchain, the number of Transactions Per Second (TPS) on the blockchain is large since all the recorded data points are directly sent to the blockchain. Considering the configurations of the mobile application, there are 250 TPS on the blockchain when the number of mobile phone users equals 1250.

B. Case 2: With Clustering and Aggregation Mechanisms

The TPS can be reduced considerably when data is clustered and aggregated before sending data to the blockchain. Considering the application configurations, for 1250 mobile application users, there are only 10 TPS on the blockchain network when data is clustered and aggregated, significantly less than the TPS value obtained when it's not clustered and aggregated. This results in lower TPS throughput and latency in the blockchain network.

Results Comparison

Fig. 5 shows the performance comparison of the network with and without an aggregation mechanism before sending data to the blockchain. The results demonstrate improved performance across all measured parameters when employing the aggregation mechanism.

The “success rate” of blockchain represents the percentage of error-free executions in transactions. The first two bars in Fig. 5 provide a comparison of success rates with and without the proposed clustering method. Notably, when utilizing this method, the success rate reaches 100%, a significant improvement compared to the scenario without it.

Moving on to the “latency” of the network, which measures the time for transaction processing and confirmation, the “Average Latency” section in Fig. 5 demonstrates negligible average latency when the aggregation method is employed. This indicates a swift and efficient processing of transactions within the blockchain network.

In terms of “throughput,” representing the network’s transaction processing capacity, Fig. 5 presents throughputs (measured in TPS) for both cases. Despite resulting in a lower TPS, the proposed aggregation method ensures a stable throughput,

in contrast to direct blockchain submission without aggregation, which exhibits instability.

Fig. 5 also provides insights into memory usage by nodes in Megabytes (MB). The reduced number of blocks due to low TPS contributes to lower memory usage, underscoring the advantageous impact of the proposed aggregation mechanism.

IV. CONCLUSION

Our study has integrated data clustering and aggregation techniques with a blockchain network, to improve the network’s performance. Numerical findings highlight the efficacy of using these methods, in terms of various performance parameters. Future developments in this system may leverage more Hyperledger Fabric features, such as private channels, for a secure decentralized RF spectrum management with dedicated channels for each service provider. Therefore, as technology advances, this research opens avenues for innovative, efficient, and secure solutions using blockchain to tackle real-world challenges.

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